

1 **HIV-1 infection and host microRNAs.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7
8 We demonstrate here activation of microRNA miR-210 encoded by MIR210HG in cells during HIV-1
9 infection. Other major microRNAs induced in human cells as a result of HIV-1 infection included miR-34
10 and miR-155.

11 Citations

12
13 1. Huang, J., Wang, F., Argyris, E., Chen, K., Liang, Z., Tian, H., Huang, W., Squires, K., Verlinghieri,
14 G. and Zhang, H., 2007. Cellular microRNAs contribute to HIV-1 latency in resting primary CD4+ T
15 lymphocytes. Nature medicine, 13(10), pp.1241-1247.

16
17 2. Nathans, R., Chu, C.Y., Serquina, A.K., Lu, C.C., Cao, H. and Rana, T.M., 2009. Cellular
18 microRNA and P bodies modulate host-HIV-1 interactions. Molecular cell, 34(6), pp.696-709.

19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
GSE247191